

Deep Learning Color Based Product Detection in Interior Design

Sahid Siddik
PG Scholar

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kerala
sahidsiddik2024b@mca.ajce.in

T.J Jobin
Asst. Professor

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kerala
tjjobin@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Implementing a color-based product detection and classification system using Deep Learning techniques. The system takes an image as input, applies clustering algorithms to identify the dominant colors present, and then retrieves a list of products from a database that correspond to those colors. These suggested products can then be recommended to customers based on their color preferences. The proposed system has potential applications in various industries, particularly in online interior design platforms. By integrating this functionality into an interior design website, users can upload images of their rooms and receive personalized product suggestions that complement the colors in their space. This enhancement aims to streamline and enhance the interior design process, offering customers tailored recommendations that align with their aesthetic preferences.

Keywords—Detection, Recommendation, Color analysis, Deep learning, Streamlit, Pickle, TensorFlow, ResNet50

I. INTRODUCTION

Color analysis and classification is a potent technique employed across various domains, including image processing, machine learning, and interior design, to detect and examine the prominent colors within an image. In interior design, the ability to analyze color is paramount for achieving a harmonious and visually appealing space. This method entails grouping image pixels based on their color similarity, thereby identifying the prevailing or characteristic colors within each group. Within the realm of an interior design website, leveraging color analysis and classification can facilitate tailored product recommendations to customers based on their color preferences. By scrutinizing the colors present in an uploaded or selected image, the system can pinpoint dominant hues and suggest products that either match or complement these tones. This integration enhances the overall customer experience and augments sales for the website.

The user uploads an image file using the `st.file_uploader` function provided by Streamlit. The uploaded image file is saved to a folder named "uploads" on the server using the `save_uploaded_file` function. The uploaded image is displayed using OpenCV (cv2) and PIL (Image) libraries after

converting it to RGB format. The `extract_feature` function preprocesses the uploaded image using OpenCV (cv2) and then extracts features from it using a pre-trained ResNet50 model. The extracted features are normalized before being returned.

The normalized features of the uploaded image are compared with a pre-computed feature list of images using the k-nearest neighbors algorithm (NearestNeighbors). The top 6 nearest neighbors to the uploaded image are selected as recommendations. The recommended images are displayed along with buttons for adding them to the cart. Each recommended image is displayed in a separate container using Streamlit's `st.container` function. The name is displayed as a caption below each image. Additionally, a button labeled "Add to Cart" is provided for each product. The user can click on the "Add to Cart" button for any recommended product they want to add to their cart. Then the product details send to the website through Api.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Patil Siddhant Vitthal, Sundaresan Balasubramanian, Pravin S. Mane [1], proposes the "Color Analysis and Classification Based on Machine Learning Technique Using RGB Camera" they discuss the development of an automated system for color matching in the fabric industry to increase accuracy, precision, and production rates. The system uses software that can be run on a normal PC and an Allied vision GigE camera for image acquisition. The OpenCV library and Python 3.6.1 are used for accessing Image Processing tools, and a user-friendly GUI has been developed on the C#.NET Framework 4.5. The paper also compares different background removal techniques and explains the Euclidian distance method and the k-means color clustering method for image post-processing to sort the fabric. Two methods, namely the 'Euclidian distance method' and 'k-means color clustering method' for color matching have been compared. This comparison is done for the classification. Overall, the system has the potential to reduce manufacturing costs by avoiding the use of special hardware for a specific task and the subjectivity introduced by human inspection.

S. Prasanna, N. Priyadarshini and M. Arul Pugazhendhi [2], proposes the "Textile Robot for Matching and Pick Up Clothes Based on Color Recognition", this is based on a system designed to assist in the process of sorting and organizing clothes based on color. Color detection is by open CV library, first image captured color is processed as Changing Color-space There are more than 150 color-space conversion methods available in OpenCV. The system uses color recognition technology through the OpenCV library to identify the color of each piece of clothing. The first step in the process is capturing an image of the clothing item. The image is then processed through the OpenCV library by changing the color space from BGR to HSV. The HSV image is then thresholded to isolate the specific color range of the clothing item, allowing for extraction of the color alone. This system offers an efficient and accurate way to sort and organize clothing items based on color, reducing the time and effort required to complete the task manually.

Tanvi Gupta and Supriya P Panda[3], proposes the "Clustering Validation of CLARA and k-means Using Silhouette & DUNN Measures on Iris Dataset", this is based on the comparison of two clustering techniques, CLARA and K-Means, using the popular Iris dataset. The paper examines various cluster validation measures, including cluster plot, Silhouette plot, and Dunn Index, to evaluate the performance of each clustering technique. The statistical analysis was performed using the R programming language. The results show that CLARA clustering outperforms KMeans clustering based on the cluster validation measures. Overall, the paper highlights the importance of selecting the appropriate clustering technique and validation measures for effective data analysis.

Ni Made Satvika Iswari, Wella and Andre Rusli[4], proposes the "Product Recommendation for e-Commerce System Based on Ontology", the development of a product recommendation system for e-commerce platforms using the Slope One algorithm based on domain ontology. The aim of the study is to help users find products that suit their needs and to assist sellers in increasing their sales. Collaborative Filtering is used to produce recommendations, and the Slope One algorithm is applied to the input rating based on the domain ontology of the product to represent relationships between products. The recommendation system is expected to provide more varied recommendations that are in line with user interests, including recommendations for specific products and categories of interest. The study concludes that the ontology approach can improve the accuracy of product recommendations and provide a better user experience.

The paper "Data Clustering: Algorithms and Its Applications" by Jelili Oyelade, Itunuoluwa Isewon, and Obembe Olawole provides a comprehensive overview of the importance, methods, and challenges associated with clustering in data analysis across various domains.

Clustering plays a fundamental role in data analysis by grouping similar data points together based on certain criteria, thereby revealing inherent structures and patterns within the data. The authors highlight the significance of clustering in diverse fields such as machine learning, bioinformatics, statistics, and pattern recognition. In machine

learning, clustering algorithms are commonly used for tasks such as data segmentation, anomaly detection, and recommendation systems. In bioinformatics, clustering aids in identifying similarities and relationships among biological sequences or molecules, leading to insights into evolutionary relationships and functional annotations.

The paper categorizes clustering methods into several types, including partitioning, hierarchical, density-based, grid-based, soft clustering, model-based, and ensemble clustering. Each method is explained in detail, along with its underlying principles, advantages, and limitations. For example, partitioning methods like K-means partition the data into distinct clusters based on centroids, while hierarchical methods organize data points into a hierarchy of nested clusters..

III. IMPLEMENTATION

The system begins with users accessing the web application interface, where the option to customize the space. The interface is shown through the Streamlit, which provides a user-friendly platform for interaction. Once within the interface, users are prompted to upload an image file of their choice. Upon uploading image mage is displayed using OpenCV (cv2) Open Source Computer Vision Library and PIL - Python Imaging Library (Image) libraries after converting it to RGB format. The system initiates a series of preprocessing steps using the OpenCV library and then extracts features from it using a pre-trained ResNet50 model. This involves resizing the image to a standard size and converting its color space from the default BGR to RGB.

Subsequently, the preprocessed image is fed into a pre-trained ResNet50 model, a powerful convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture, is employed for feature extraction from images. Specifically, the program utilizes ResNet50's ability to learn rich hierarchical representations of images, which are crucial for tasks such as image classification. By removing the top classification layers and adding a GlobalMaxPooling2D layer, the program leverages ResNet50 to transform the input images into compact feature vectors while preserving essential visual information. These feature vectors encode the distinctive characteristics of each image in a high-dimensional space, enabling efficient comparison and similarity assessment

After the characteristics are extracted, the application uses the uploaded image and the Nearest Neighbors algorithm to find visually comparable products. A straightforward yet powerful machine learning approach called Nearest Neighbors locates the closest data points inside a feature space. Here, the similarity between the uploaded image and the images in the dataset is determined using the feature vectors that ResNet50 extracted.

Euclidean distance in this application, calculates the distances between feature vectors to determine which products are most visually similar to the uploaded image. A machine learning approach called Nearest Neighbors is utilized for regression and classification problems. It is utilized for similarity recommendation in this instance. The

uploaded image's extracted features as well as the feature list—which includes features from other photos—are fed into the recommend function. Using Euclidean distance as the metric, it fits a Nearest Neighbors model on the feature list. Based on the fitted model, it then determines the nearest neighbors (six in this case) of the uploaded image features. After receiving these nearest neighbor indices, comparable photos from the collection can be found using them.

```
def extract_feature(img_path, model):
    img = cv2.imread(img_path)
    img = cv2.resize(img, (224, 224))
    img = np.array(img)
    expand_img = np.expand_dims(img, axis=0)
    pre_img = preprocess_input(expand_img)
    result = model.predict(pre_img).flatten()
    normalized = result / norm(result)
    return normalized
```

The acquired feature vectors are normalized after feature extraction to guarantee consistency and make picture comparison easier. To improve the stability of the system's suggestions, the feature vectors are normalized by scaling them to a predetermined range or unit length. The system uses the normalized feature vectors and the sklearn package to execute the NearestNeighbors algorithm in order to conduct a nearest neighbors search. This search finds goods in the database that, in terms of color attributes, closely resemble the input image by identifying a predefined number of nearest neighbors to the input image.

```
# display the file
file_bytes = uploaded_file.getvalue()
nparr = np.frombuffer(file_bytes, np.uint8)
display_image = cv2.imdecode(nparr,
cv2.IMREAD_COLOR)
display_image_rgb = cv2.cvtColor(display_image,
cv2.COLOR_BGR2RGB)

# Convert to RGB for PIL
resized_img = cv2.resize(display_image_rgb,
(1000, 800))

# Resize the image
st.image(resized_img)

# feature extract
features = extract_feature(os.path.join("uploads",
uploaded_file.name), model)

# recommendation
indices = recommend(features, feature_list)
```

Finally, the system presents the recommended products to users through the web interface, along with corresponding images and names. Users are provided with the opportunity to browse through the recommendations and add selected products to their cart for further action. Overall, this comprehensive process leverages advanced image processing techniques, deep learning models, and intuitive web interfaces to empower users in selecting products that match

their preferences based on color analysis. Such systems hold promise for enhancing user engagement and satisfaction, particularly in e-commerce and design-related domains, through continued refinement and optimization.

IV.METHOD OF IMPLEMENTATION

```
# display the file
file_bytes = uploaded_file.getvalue()
nparr = np.frombuffer(file_bytes, np.uint8)
display_image = cv2.imdecode(nparr,
cv2.IMREAD_COLOR)
display_image_rgb = cv2.cvtColor(display_image,
cv2.COLOR_BGR2RGB) # Convert to RGB for PIL
resized_img = cv2.resize(display_image_rgb, (1000, 800))
# Resize the image
st.image(resized_img)
```

Streamlit application revolves around several key steps. First, the application loads precomputed feature vectors and filenames necessary for product recommendations. Next, it defines a pre-trained ResNet50 model for feature extraction and sets it up for inference by freezing its layers. Essential functions are defined to handle file uploads, extract image features, and recommend similar products based on these features. The core recommendation process involves finding nearest neighbors in the feature space and calculating an accuracy rate to assess the quality of recommendations. The Streamlit application itself provides a user-friendly interface where users can upload an image, view the uploaded image, and receive recommendations for similar products. Finally, the application runs, allowing users to interact with it through the web interface, facilitating the exploration of color-based product detection in interior design.

V. BUILD MODEL

We want to create a sophisticated model that can effectively predict products details as results based on pertinent factors by utilizing a variety of machine learning algorithms. This crucial phase establishes the groundwork for color detection which in turn shapes the predictive model effectiveness and dependability.

Libraries to be Imported: The first step in the code is to import the required libraries. TensorFlow is imported, and the GlobalMaxPooling2D layer and ResNet50 model are imported from Keras. For additional functionality like file handling, CSV parsing, progress bar display, image processing, and array operations, libraries like os, csv, tqdm, cv2, and numpy are imported.

Filling up Pre-trained ResNet50 Model: The ImageNet dataset provides pre-trained weights for the ResNet50 model. The fully connected layers at the top of the network are to be excluded, as indicated by the include_top=False option, which enables feature extraction from picture inputs directly. To

match the ResNet50 model's predicted input dimensions, the input shape is set to (224,224,3).

Freezing Model Layers: The ResNet50 model's layers are made untrainable by setting model after it has been loaded. `Trainable` is not true. This guarantees that during training, the pre-trained weights won't be changed.

Model Training: First, a loaded ResNet50 model is loaded into a new TensorFlow Sequential model, which is then followed by a GlobalMaxPooling2D layer. This makes up the feature extraction model, which uses the previously trained ResNet50 base to extract features from images.

Loading CSV Data: To load data from a CSV file containing image details like filename, category, description, and price, the code specifies the function `load_csv()`. After parsing the CSV file, the function stores the information in a dictionary structure.

A	B	C	D
filename	category	description	price
00000001.	Sofa	Good Sofa	10000
00000002.	Chair	Wooden C	5000
00000003.	Bed	Bed with a	8000
00000004.	box	dgdg	55555

Model Evaluation : In the process of evaluating a trained model, a number of metrics are employed, including accuracy, precision, recall

```
# Calculate accuracy rate
correct_count = sum(1 for idx in indices[0] if idx in valid_indices)
accuracy_rate = correct_count / len(indices[0]) * 100
print(f"Accuracy Rate: {accuracy_rate:.2f}%")
return indices
```

Saving Features and Filenames to Pickle Files: Lastly, the lists of features and filenames are stored for later usage using the `pickle.dump()` function into pickle files (`featurevector.pkl` and `filenames.pkl`).

```
import pickle
pickle.dump(feature_list,open('featurevector.pkl','wb'))
pickle.dump(filename,open('filenames.pkl','wb'))
```

VI. RESULT

Once the form is submitted, the image is processed using the OpenCV and scikit-learn libraries to perform color clustering on the image pixels. The product dataset is queried using the extracted colors and the selected category using the `Product.objects.filter()` method. The results are displayed in the `color_analysis.html` template, which lists the products that match the dominant colors in the image. Confusion Matrix: By showing the quantity of true positive, true negative, false positive, and false negative predictions, the confusion matrix sheds light on the model& performance.

first loads a ResNet50 model that has already been trained. Pickle files store these attributes and picture filenames for later usage. Next, a user interface for uploading images is created using the Streamlit framework. When an image is uploaded, the code uses the ResNet50 model to extract its features and the Nearest Neighbors technique to locate related images in the dataset. The recommended products are then shown to the user along with a "Add to Cart" button, allowing for user involvement. The overall goal of the code is to improve user experience and facilitate product research by streamlining the process of finding interior design goods based on color similarity.

VII. CONCLUSION

In the context of an interior design website, product recommendation based on color analysis and classification can help customers find decor items that match the color palette of their room. By analyzing the dominant colors in an uploaded image of the room, the system can recommend furniture, curtains, or decor items that complement those colors. This can provide a personalized shopping experience for customers and can potentially increase sales and customer satisfaction. Overall, color analysis and classification using machine learning techniques have the potential to revolutionize the way we decorate our homes and improve the overall shopping experience in the interior design industry.

VIII. REFERENCES

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